

**DEVELOPMENT OF AN UNSUPERVISED SUBJECTIVE AND
OBJECTIVE SYSTEM**

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CERTIFICATION

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DEDICATION

This project is dedicated to Almighty God and to our parents who helped us to make this project a success.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I acknowledge GOD and all those who stood up for me in ensuring that this work is done with speed and efficiency. I can't do without mentioning names; Dr Doyin Ajayi. Thank you sir, your impact is greatly felt. God bless you.

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the study

Artificial intelligence is the engineering and science of making intelligent machines that aim to understand the nature of human intelligence through the construction of intelligent computer programs that imitate intelligent behavior, it also the development of intelligence in the machines or software and provide them the ability to think like humans. There is a great impact of machine learning on society as we are surrounded with technology. Machine learning is one of the older and an extraordinary domain area of artificial intelligence and concerns the study of computational methods for the discovery of new knowledge and for the management of existing knowledge. Machine learning tasks can be classified into the following two groups:

- i. Supervised learning: This kind of learning is also known as learning from examples. In this learning, the training set contains data and the correct output of the task with that data.
- ii. Unsupervised learning: This kind of learning is also known as learning from observation. In this learning, the training set contains data but no solutions; the computer must find the solutions on its own.

Automation is an aspect of artificial intelligence which can either be supervised or unsupervised, which helps to automate the assessment of answers by using a computer, the automated scoring system is a system based on web technology that expands the flexibility of the examination and ensure the safety of the answers. A lot of different methods are used in marking both subjective and objective questions such as the ones listed below:

- i. The Project Essay Grade (PEG) in which the design approach is based on the concept of “proxies”, i.e. computer approximations or measures of trims, intrinsic variables of interest within the essay to simulate human rater grading.
- ii. The Intelligent Essay Assessor (IEA) which is based on the Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA) technique.
- iii. The Educational Testing Service (ETS I) which uses the lexical-semantic techniques to build a scoring system.

- iv. The Electronic Essay Rater (E-RATER) which uses a combination of statistical and natural language processing (NLP) techniques to extract linguistic features from the essays to be graded.
- v. The Conceptual Rater (C-RATER), which is a natural language processing (NLP) based prototype;
- vi. The Bayesian Essay Test Scoring System (BETSY), which is a program that classifies text based on trained material.
- vii. The Auto mark which employs natural language processing (NLP) techniques to mark open-ended responses. Etc.

Not all of the above-listed ways of grading with a computer is really efficient, with the use of natural language processing in combination with a neural network the accuracy and speed of grading of a computer would be close to that of human. Both natural language processing and neural networks are part of artificial intelligence, the neural network is made up of neurons connected to each other; at the same time, each connection of the neural network is associated with a weight that dictates the importance of its relationship in the neuron when multiplied by the input value. Also, Natural language processing is a subfield of linguistics, computer science, information engineering and artificial intelligence concerned with the interactions between computers and human languages, in particular how to program a computer to process and analyze large amounts of natural language data.

1.2 Statement of the problem

As students' numbers in College, university or secondary school is getting larger, the traditional way of grading students is serving as a burden to teachers, the grading of the students is now a great challenge for the teachers, the complex and various work such as the need to set questions, set types, invigilate, correct, record scores and add up the score cost them a lot of energy, time and spending, below is the summary of the effect the traditional way of grading provides:

- i. Time-consuming when grading.
- ii. Cost it takes to grade.

- iii. The unfairness of the person grading.

The problem teachers faced while grading such as the time and the cost it takes to completely grade many students as made the teachers manipulate their responsibilities and often limit students writing opportunities to make grading easier, which in turn affects students writing skills. Also, the use of paper to gather information is time-consuming and costly.

Different methods has been made to solve the problems listed above, different automated scoring system each with their own capabilities and these systems has proven to be accurate and reliable, but most of them are not providing accurate and they take time to grade both in the subjective and objective part or some can only grade either of the two and not the two. The main goal of this project is to improve the automated systems so that they can work perfectly like human graders and give it the ability to grade both the subjective and objective types of questions. The research focuses on making an automatic system that can grade at a fast rate with accuracy and help reduce the adverse effects of human factors.

1.3 Aims and Objective of the study

The specific objectives of the research are to:

- i. Design a subjective and objective web application that can grade accurately at fast speed.
- ii. Implementing the model in schools to help reduce the paperwork and to eliminate manual processes and to save significant staff time, reduces the manpower required and provides accurate information always

1.4 Scope of the study

The scope of this work is to develop an automated objective and subjective scoring system that will improve how teachers/lecturers can score a student perfectly without following the traditional method. And the record of the department of computer science at Ekiti state University will be put into consideration for the achievement of the proposed study.

1.5 Research methodology

Automated essay scoring is a measurement technology in which computers evaluate written work. The system is divided into few parts, below is a brief explanation of different parts

- i. **The website front end:** This is where the user interacts with, both the students and the admin (Lecturer or teacher).
- ii. **The objective marking system:** this system stores all the answer gotten from the admin in the database and compares it with the student's choice to grade them.
- iii. **The subjective marking system:** This makes use of Machine learning methods where we get the vector of each word in the answer of the students and the answer of the lecturers and then find the average of the two vectors and perform cosine similarities to see how close they are.

We are going to make use of word2vec created by Google to convert the text of both the lecturer or teacher and students into vectors, but first, we would import all the libraries we would use in python such as the genism, NLTK, etc., then train the word2vec with Google corpus then both the input of the student and the teacher would pass through below steps because machines struggle to deal with raw text data. In fact, it's almost impossible for machines to deal with anything except for numerical data.

- i. Remove Noisy Data

In regular sentences, Noisy data can be defined as text file header, footer, HTML, XML, markup data. As these types of data are not meaningful and does not provide any information so it is mandatory to remove this type of noisy data. In python HTML, XML would be removed by BeautifulSoup library while markup, the header would be removed by using regular expression

- ii. Tokenization

In tokenization we convert group of sentence into token. It is also called text segmentation or lexical analysis. It is basically splitting data into small chunk of words. We would use python's NLTK library's word tokenize () function to achieve this.

- iii. Stemming

Stemming is a process of reducing words to their word stem, base or root form. So we would do that to both inputs.

iv. Lemmatization

The aim of lemmatization, like stemming, is to reduce inflectional forms to a common base form.

After the two inputs have passed through the processes above then we would pass them through the word2vec to get the vector of each words. Then we find the average and perform cosine similarity to get how close they are and grade it.

1.6 Significance of the study

Technology is advancing and making life easier for human use, the automatic subjective and objective questions of marking is a key technology in the education system. The study of the development of a supervised automated subjective and objective scoring system can be of use in both the secondary level and university level to enhance the school processes; a system for the automated assessment would be consistent in the way it scores essays, and enormous cost and time savings could be achieved.

The application would provide a solution to the problems teachers/lecturers faced while grading students such as the time it takes the energy and the cost, also the system would provide accuracy while grading so that the system can be applied to teaching practice. The system can also be used to evaluate both long and short questions answers.

Also the system will evaluate all the use of paper and manual scoring and also the risk associated with it. One of the risk using traditional (manual scoring) method is the teachers/lecturers can misplace a student script or manipulate a student score. This system also allows the institution management (Admin) track or investigate student score in a particular course or subject.

1.7 Definition of terms

i. **Automated:** Automation is an aspect of artificial intelligence which can either be supervised or unsupervised, which helps to automate the assessment of answers by using a computer, the

automated scoring system is a system based on web technology that expands the flexibility of the examination and ensures the safety of the answers.

- ii. **Scoring System:** Scoring system is a system of classification to quality or merit or amount rating system.
- iii. **Supervised learning:** This kind of learning is also known as learning from examples. In this learning, the training set contains data and the correct output of the task with that data.
- iv. **Unsupervised learning:** This kind of learning is also known as learning from observation. In this learning, the training set contains data but no solutions; the computer must find the solutions on its own.
- v. **Objective Question:** Objective questions are those questions that require a specific answer.
- vi. **Subjective Question:** Subjective questions are those questions that requires answers in an explanatory form.
- vii. **Artificial intelligence:** Artificial intelligence is the engineering and science of making intelligent machines that aim to understand the nature of human intelligence through the construction of intelligent computer programs that imitate intelligent behavior, it also the development of intelligence in the machines or software and provide them the ability to think like humans.
- viii. **Machine Learning:** machine learning is a sun-area of artificial intelligence, whereby the term refers to the ability of IT systems to independently find solution to problems by recognizing patterns in databases.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter present a review of the research related to the development of an unsupervised automated subjective and objective scoring system by looking at the various definitions provided by authorities on the subject, the concept, objective, uses and purposes.

2.1 An overview of current research on automated essay grading

Author: Valenti et al., (2003)

2.1.1 Introduction

This research talks about how essay is a useful tool to assess learning outcomes, it went forward to let us know that assessment plays a central role in education process, but there are effects in the way each assessment are graded, such as:

- i. Time consuming when grading.
- ii. Cost it takes to grade.
- iii. Unfairness of the person grading.

Based on above issues there is need to create an automated assessment tool for automated system would at least be consistent in the way it scores essay, and fast in grading, time saving and enormous cost could be achieved. The research went on to list and explain 10 automated systems currently available, which are Project Essay Grade (PEG), Intelligent Essay Assessor (IEA), Educational Testing service I, Electronic Essay Rater (E-Rater), C-Rater, BETSY, Intelligent Essay Marking System, SEAR, Paperless School free text Marking Engine and Auto mark. The main Purpose of this research is to present a survey of current approaches to the automated assessment system.

2.1.2 Statement of the problem

From the research the main problem faced when not using an automated scoring system are:

- i. Time consuming when grading, According to Mason (2002), about 30% of teachers' time is devoted to marking. "So, if we want to free up that 30%, then we must find an effective way, that teacher will trust, to mark essays and short text responses."
- ii. The perceived subjectivity of the grading process, Many researchers claim that the subjective nature of essay assessment leads to variation in grades awarded by different human assessors, which is perceived by students as a great source of unfairness.
- iii. Cost it takes to grade.

2.1.3 Methodology

The research presented different automated systems available to solve the problem gotten from not using an automated scoring system, the research presented below systems:

- i. **The Project Essay Grade (PEG)** in which the design approach is based on the concept of "proxes", i.e. computer approximations or measures of *trins*, *intrinsic* variables of interest within the essay to simulate human rater grading. PEG relies on a statistical approach based on the assumption that the quality of essays is reflected by the measurable proxes and primarily on style analysis of surface linguistic features of a block of text.
- ii. **The Intelligent Essay Assessor (IEA)** which is based on the Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA) technique, the main features of IEA include relatively low unit cost, quick customized feedback, and plagiarism detection.
- iii. **The Educational Testing Service (ETS I)** which uses the lexical-semantic techniques to build a scoring system, It uses a domain-specific, concept-based lexicon and a concept grammar, both built from training data.
- iv. **The Electronic Essay Rater (E-RATER)** which uses a combination of statistical and natural language processing (NLP) techniques to extract linguistic features from the essays to be graded. It assigns a score for writing skills.
- v. **The Conceptual Rater (C-RATER)**, which is a natural language processing (NLP) based prototype; the c-rater is aimed to score a response as being either correct or incorrect.
- vi. **The Bayesian Essay Test Scoring System (BETSY)**, which is a program that classifies text based on trained material.
- vii. **The Intelligent Essay Marking Systems (IEMS)** that is based on the pattern indexing neural network (the indextron), the system can be used both as an assessment tools and for

diagnostic and tutoring purposes in many content-based subjects. Students are given immediate feedback and can learn where and why they had done well or not made the grade.

- viii. ***The Auto mark*** which employs natural language processing (NLP) techniques to mark open-ended responses. It looks for specific content within free-text answers, the content being specified in the form of a number of marking scheme templates.
- ix. ***The Schema Extract Analyze and Report (SEAR)*** which requires the assessment both of style and content (where appropriate). Thus, the system provides an expandable, flexible method for the automated marking of the essay content and provides a method for the automated marking of the essay style too.
- x. ***The Paperless School Free-Text Marking Engine (PS-ME)*** which is designed as an integrated component of a web-based learning management system (Mason & Groves-Stephenson, 2002) and is still under development. Due to its processing requirements, the PSME does not grade essays in real-time.

2.1.4 Significance of the study

The study of the development of an unsupervised automated subjective and objective scoring system can be of use in both the secondary level and university level to enhance the school processes; a system for automated assessment would be consistent in the way it scores essays, and enormous cost and time savings could be achieved.

2.1.5 Limitation of the study

The most common problems encountered in the research on automated essay grading are the absence of a good standard to calibrate human marks and of a clear set of rules for selecting master texts.

2.2 Research and Design of Online System Based on Subjective Questions Automatic Scoring

Author: Shu, Y. (2016).

2.2.1 Introduction

As students' numbers in College, university or secondary school is getting larger, grading of the students is now a great challenge for the teachers, the complex and various work such as the need to set questions, set types, invigilate, correct, record scores and add up the score cost them a lot of energy and spending, this leads to creating of an automated scoring system.

The automated scoring system is a system based on web technology that expands the flexibility of the examination and ensures the safety of the answers, this system based on the research is really good at objective questions but for the subjective it difficult for the computer to realize the automatic scoring of subjective questions.

2.2.2 Statement of the problem

The traditional way of grading students is serving as a burden to teachers nowadays due to the large numbers of college, secondary or university students, this old way of grading also is costly, time and energy taking, this research researched on how the teachers heavy burden can be solved using an automated scoring system and also ways in which the system can be perfected to score students accurately.

2.2.3 Methodology

The steps below are followed to grade subjective questions:

Step 1: Preprocessing of Clauses

Processing of clauses divides a text into many sentences with a critical limitation of punctuation.

Step 2: Preprocessing of Participle

Participles refer to countless meaningful words that are divided in the coherent characters sequence. Here the algorithm of the clause is divided based on:

- i. The matching of strings.
- ii. The statistics.
- iii. The understanding.

Step 3 Processing of Key Words

The computer makes the judgment by the key words when matching the students' answers with the reference versions. The key words are divided into two types:

- i. General Key word: These are the key words of the text rather than the point scores.

- ii. Necessary key words: These are the essential parts and are the point scores of the students' answers.

Step 4 Processing of Matching

This is the matching arithmetic based on the key words, for example the calculating methods based on the vector space model.

Step 5 Calculating Inclination/Calculation of Inclination

This deals with the calculation of the similarity of each sentence by applying to the inclination arithmetic of fuzzy mathematics.

Step 6 Dealing with Scoring

In here Multiplication of the similarity of each sentence with the corresponding weighted value to add up the scores of each sentence, and it is the final score of the student.

2.2.4 Significance of the study

The main focus of the research is to provide solution to the problems teachers faced while grading students such as the time it takes the energy and the cost, also the development of a system that would provide accuracy while grading, so that the system can be applied to teaching practice.

2.2.5 Limitation of the study

Scoring standard needs to be rationalized, the way the presently used automated system is operating is not providing an accurate grade because all it does is to preprocess the matching sentences with key words and this cannot take the rationality of the sentence and the sequence into consideration, and the matching results are not ideal. So it is necessary to find a more intelligent solution.

2.3 The Design and Implementation of Subjective Questions Automatic Scoring Algorithm in Intelligent Tutoring System

Authors: Xia et al. (2013)

2.3.1 Introduction

Network Exam has not only convenient organization but also can work anytime, anywhere and can quickly and objectively give test scores. This research analyze the way teacher review subjective questions and then introduce the concept of one way approach degree based on the nearness theory of fuzzy mathematics. The research provides solutions to the problems faced during grading students.

2.3.2 Statement of the problem

Automatic subjective question of marking is a key technology in the education system. The research focus on making the automatic system answers the characteristics of different kinds of questions and to achieve fast, accurate automatic scoring and reduce the adverse effects of human factors.

2.3.3 Methodology

The way teachers review subjective questions is such that, they first check the student answers a few score points, score points as many high scores. Then look at the student's answer and standard answer and score. Finally, consider the students answer whether the language fluent, clarity and other factors appropriate to adjust the score. The introduction of the one way approach is to have the ability to measure the closeness of student answer and standard answer (two fuzzy sets); the following define the concept of one-way nearness the author proposed in the research.

Definition 1: Let $U = \{U_1, U_2, U_3, \dots, U_n\}$, $A, B \in F(U)$. If the mapping $\delta: F(U) \times F(U) \rightarrow [0, 1]$, satisfies the condition:

- $\delta(A, A) = 1$
- $\delta(B, B) = 1$
- If the $A \subset B$ or $A \supset B$, then $\delta(A, B) \geq \delta(A, C)$ and said $\delta(A, B)$, A is close to the B unidirectional closeness degree.

Definition 2: Let A, B is the string, A contain n characters, $\delta(A, B)$ represent A close to the B unidirectional closeness. In accordance with the order from left to right, the effective sum number of set A in each element in the Set B refers to m, $\delta(A, B) = m/n$. It is easy to verify that it meets the definition of a one-way approach degree. From above:

- i. the standard answer string is denoted by A_0

- ii. students answer string is denoted by A ,
- iii. A_0 and A are two fuzzy sets.

One-way approach degree $\delta (A_0, A)$.

2.3.4 Significance of the study

The introduction of the one way approach method allow students answers to be compared with the standard answer to so as to achieve fast, accurate automatic scoring and reduce the adverse effects of human factors. Thus it can promote the standardized and scientific examination.

2.3.5 Limitation of the study

The system designed in this research is just to compare the standard answer with the student answer and the limitation of this method is that it does not check for clarity and other factors appropriate to adjust the score.

2.4 A Gentle Introduction to Automated Scoring

Author: Corey (2017).

2.4.1 Introduction

Students in USA are not performing well in their writing skills and this general lack of writing is carried to the workplace which causes employee lot of money to remedy the writing deficiency. Teachers also manipulate their responsibilities and often limit students writing opportunities to make grading easier, this greatly affect students writing skills.

So there is need for the introduction of a solution to the above problems, the automated scoring system is built and designed to provide solutions to address the problems explained above. The system is meant to allow students to extensively practice their writing skills and provide students regular feedback, so that students' writing performance will substantively improve.

2.4.2 Statement of the problem

The problem teachers faced while grading such as the time and the cost it takes to completely grade many students as made the teachers manipulate their responsibilities and often

limit students writing opportunities to make grading easier, which in turn affect students writing skills.

2.4.3 Methodology

The automated scoring system that provide solution to the problem uses machine learning to determine how features of response relate to score assigned by experts, this system do not read the students response the way we people do, but it match various characteristics of responses with the score assigned by experts raters and use this relations to predict scores for new response.

2.4.4 Significance of the study

From the research it found out that researchers found that students who used an automated writing-evaluation program wrote and revised more and were more motivated to write. Teachers also reported that automated writing evaluation reduced their grading burden and supported individualized instruction (Warschauer & Grimes, 2008). Students benefit most from specific, detailed writing feedback such as score report that includes spelling and grammar feedback, feedback for each of six traits of writing quality, and also holistic and trait scores for each essay composed or revised.

The most significant of the study is that the system is tend to improve the quality of student writing and tends to be accurate. Furthermore, automated-scoring engines are perfectly reliable.

2.4.5 Limitation of the study

The automated system may be tricked by students and receive undeserved scores, for example a student can provide answers with complex syntax and vocabulary, also this system compromise the social nature of writing and risks replacing teachers feedback.

2.5 An Automated Assessment System for Evaluation of Students' Answers Using Novel Similarity Measures

Authors: Madhumitha and Ilango. (2016).

2.5.1 Introduction

Automation is an aspect of artificial intelligence, computer assisted assessment helps to automate the assessment of answers by using computer, the research proposed an automated assessment system which evaluate students short and long answer, it made know that evaluation of answer is based on six types of questions according to bloom's taxonomy, those six questions are synthesis, analysis, application, comprehension, information recall and evaluation question.

The proposed system can only evaluate two of the questions which are the comprehension and information recall type question.

2.5.2 Statement of the problem

Objective question system are more common because they are easy to create and use, but the subjective automation scoring system built only focus mostly on short answers and not long answer, which is a problem. Also most of the automated systems consider many training essays and answers to evaluate student answer.

2.5.3 Methodology

The proposed system follows below diagram to score or grade a student.

Figure 2.1: The system structure

The system works like this, student answer and teacher answer in the text form are stored in the text file, and then the sentence segmentation segments both the teacher answer and student answer into individual sentences. Then the POS tagger extracts the part of speech from both the teacher and student answer and stores them separately. Next the sentence similarity computation modules compare the key points in both the teacher answer and student answer, and then the scoring module gives the score.

2.5.4 Significance of the study

The system can be used to evaluate both long and short essay answers and it can also evaluates the information recall and comprehension type answers in Bloom’s taxonomy.

2.5.5 Limitation of the study

The system cannot evaluate questions that have to do with application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation.

2.6 Automated Essay Scoring

Author: Semire (2006).

2.6.1 Introduction

Teachers responding to student's research can be of burden particularly when the students are large in number because they would have to grade the essay and give feedback to each student's essay; this is also waste lot of time. Computers have been of great assistance; the automated grading system would help the teachers in reducing their burden and allow them to make essential use of their time due to that it provide students with a score as well as feedback within seconds.

2.6.2 Statement of the problem

We have different automated scoring system each with their own capabilities and these systems has proven to be accurate and reliable but some has to be improved so at to attain excellence in machine scoring of essays to increase the accuracy and effectiveness of the systems.

2.6.3 Methodology

Different systems are used in accessing essay with different methods, below is a list of them:

- i. **Project Essay Grader (PEG):** PEG uses proxy measures to predict the intrinsic quality of the essays. Proxies refer to the particular writing construct such as average word length, essay length, number of semicolons or commas, and so on (Rudner & Gagne, 2001).
- ii. **Intelligent Essay Assessor (IEA):** This automated system analyzes and scores an essay using a semantic text analysis method called Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA) (Lemaire & Dessus, 2001). Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA) is defined as "a statistical model of word usage that permits comparisons of the semantic similarity between pieces of textual information.

- iii. **E-Raters and Criterion:** It analyzes the quality of an essay by identifying linguistic features in the text (Burstein & Marcu, 2000; Burstein, 2003). E-rater uses natural language processing (NLP) techniques, which identify specific lexical and syntactic cues in a text, to analyze essays. The Natural language processing has four categories of language tasks which include speech recognition, syntactic analysis, discourse analysis and information extraction, and machine translation. Criterion relies on Educational Testing Service (ETS) technologies called “e-rater” and “Critique” Writing Analysis tools.
- iv. **Intellimetric and Myaccess:** IntelliMetric, an AES system developed by Vantage Learning, is known as the first essay scoring tool that was based on artificial intelligence (AI) (Raymat, & Barrera, 2003). Like e-rater, IntelliMetric relies on NLP, which determines “the meaning of a text by parsing the text in known ways according to known rules conforming to the rules of English language”. MY Access is known as the instructional application of IntelliMetric, it is a web-based writing assessment tool.

2.6.4 Significance of the study

The automated grading system is of great help to the educational system, it helps overcome time, cost and generalizability issues in writing assessment. Excellence in these machines would help enhance and support education system perfectly.

2.6.5 Limitation of the study

One short coming of a computer is that it needs an instruction before it can execute, so therefore computers could not assess an essay as human raters do because the computer would do “what it is programmed to do” and it wouldn’t “appreciate” an essay; another criticism is the construct objections. That is, the computer counts variables that might not be “truly” important in essay grading, i.e., focusing on formal (Chung & O’Neil, 1997), also each automated systems all need to be trained on large numbers of essay samples in order to be able to evaluate the student essays effectively.

2.7 Automated Essay scoring with the E-rater System

Author: Attali (2013).

2.7.1 Introduction

The use of essay writing assessments in large-scale testing programs has been greatly expanded in recent years, E-rater is one of the mostly used automated scoring systems, the research reviews e-rater's feature set, the framework for feature aggregation into essay scores, processes for the evaluation of e-rater scores, and options for operational implementation, with an emphasis on the standards and procedures used at ETS to ensure scoring quality.

2.7.2 Statement of the problem

The research talked about how E-rater system process and grade essay to ensure scoring quality.

2.7.3 Methodology

Automated scoring systems do not actually read and understand essays as humans do, this system evaluate variables of interest, such as diction, fluency, and grammar, in order to produce an essay score, E-rater scoring is based on automatically extracting features of the essay text using Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques. These features measure several underlying aspects of the writing construct: word choice, grammatical conventions (grammar, usage, and mechanics), development and organization, and topical vocabulary usage.

2.7.4 Significance of the study

The drawback of large-scale essay writing assessments is that their evaluation is a complex and time-consuming process associated with significant costs. E-rater has helped solve the large scale essay assessment by grading at fast speed and also used it provide score reporting and diagnostic feedback, it changes students writing strategies and it used by teachers as a practice tool and instructional aid.

2.7.5 Limitation of the study

A major issue in developing a scoring scheme is the determination of feature weights. Weights represent the relative importance of the different features. Different weighting schemes will result in scores that have different meanings depending on the features that are emphasized.

Therefore, the choice of a weighting scheme and its rationale is of utmost importance for the validity of an automated scoring system.

2.8 College Automation System

Authors: Pooja et al (2016)

2.8.1 Introduction

The introduction of an automation system to school to help manage college management using single platform, with the help of this system the school can gather all the useful information needed to the management in few clicks.

2.8.2 Statement of the problem

The use of research to gather information is time consuming and costly, the main purpose of the system is to create software which will manage the working of different modules in a school. The interconnectivity among modules reduces the time to perform different operational task. The objective of the system is to reduce the paper work, eliminate manual processes and to save significant staff time.

2.8.3 Methodology

Figure 2.2: The system process

The system provide students with the ability access to personal profile, current attendance record, Class Tests records, Daily Class Routines and all the notifications and upcoming events which are managed by admin.

The system also allows staff to manage all the data of their subjects of respective class. They can manage daily attendance of all students of respective subjects and classes. Staff members are able to give notifications and can upload some documents related to their respective subjects. Staff can generate the daily, monthly or yearly report of individual student as well as class. Mark sheet generation and time table generation facility is also available for staff. Instead of manual work this application gives automatic work department and the Admin can manage the accounts of the all the students and staff. All the logs of student information can be view and manage by Admin itself. Admin can also upload notices regarding admission forms etc. Admin can view all the students and approve.

2.8.4 Significance of the study

Technology is advancing and making life easier for human use, the objective of the system is to reduce the paper work and to eliminate manual processes and to save significant staff time, reduces the man power required and provides accurate information always.

2.8.5 Limitation of the study

The database with which data is stored can crash, and also lot of design is to be done to create the system.

2.9 Automated Essay Scoring: Writing Assessment and Instruction

Author: Shermis et al (2010).

2.9.1 Introduction

The greatest hindrance to having secondary students write more was the requirement that, ultimately, a teacher had to review stacks of papers, but with the introduction of automated system, it now easy to give feedback and grade students. The automated scoring system server as both an assessment and instruction system, letting student have access to technology that would provide quick feedback on their writing serve as a great benefit to the students.

2.9.2 Statement of the problem

The main problem with the old way of grading is that it takes teachers lot of time and it stresses them to review stacks of papers. The automated essay scoring system provide an easy way to grade and give feedback to each students, making it easy for teachers to use their time for other useful things within the school.

2.9.3 Methodology

Automated essay scoring is a measurement technology in which computers evaluate written work (Shermis & Burstein, 2003). The system context is to analyze the written text into its observable components. Page and Peterson (1995) referred to observable components as “proxes” or approximations for underlying “trins” (i.e., intrinsic characteristics) of writing, proxes. An example of a simple prox is essay length; an example of a complex prox might be a count of the number of times “because” is used in an essay.

The evaluation of content by the system may be accomplished through the specification of vocabulary, with six areas of analysis: errors in grammar, usage and mechanics style (Burstein, 2003). Identification of organizational segments, such as thesis statement and vocabulary content. These sets include content, word variety, grammar, text complexity, and sentence variety. Word variety refers to word complexity or word uniqueness.

The NLP capabilities used to generate these adaptations include, automatic summarization (Marcu,2000), machine translation, and synonym and antonym identification.

2.9.4 Significance of the study

The automated essay scoring is an effort to offer additional writing practice to students; the system also offer more descriptive essay feedback similar to teacher feedback of student writing such as indications of grammar, usage, and mechanics errors, stylistic, and organization and development issues.

2.9.5 Limitation of the study

The automated essay scoring might still be characterized as an emerging technology which still needs to be enhanced to do more proficient and accurate work.

2.10 Automated Essay Grading

Authors: Adamson et al., (2014)

2.10.1 Introduction

Using machine learning to assess human writing is both an interesting challenge and can potentially make quality education more accessible. This research focused on finding out which features were more useful in predicting the score of the essay. They explored methods of giving more detailed feedback for essays, such as levels of coherence and technical correctness.

2.10.2 Statement of the problem

Since we have different types of automated system with different features in grading students, the research main focus is to learn which features were more useful in predicting the score of the essay, which one would closely match those made by human graders.

2.10.3 Methodology

Feature extraction is what automated system use in grading, below are the features

- i. .Word n-grams - N-grams tokenize the next and treat it as a bag of words", where each feature is a count of how many times a word or combination of words appeared.
- ii. Part of speech n-grams - Natural Language Toolkit part of speech tagger is used,
- iii. Character counts
- iv. Word counts
- v. Sentence counts
- vi. Number of misspelling
- vii. Reduced dimension term-vector using Latent Semantic Analysis

Latent Semantic Analysis is a method that attempts to find a set of concepts that run through a set of documents. LSA starts with a term-document matrix (a matrix where documents are represented along one axis, and counts of terms are represented along the other axis).

The Singular Value Decomposition was used to represent the matrix as a product of two orthogonal matrices and a diagonal matrix.

2.10.4 Significance of the study

The research talked about which features were more useful in predicting the score of the essay, so an experiment was carried out. From the experiment carried out, it founded that the models are able to make predictions that closely match those made by human graders also they explored methods of giving more detailed feedback for essays, such as levels of coherence and technical correctness. The Support Vector Regression was able to make predictions that matched closely with human graders. Using LSA is able to capture relationships between terms that are not equal, but have similar meanings or concepts, for example "dog" and "hound".

2.10.5 Limitation of the study

It was noted that Word count did not play as big of a factor as originally believed. Latent Semantic Analysis was less successful in producing predictions that agreed with human graders. They also found that essays that generally had a greater score would have a higher percentage of coherent sentences.

2.11 Automated essay scoring using machine learning

Authors: Singh and Pant (2019)

2.11.1 Introduction

Automated Essay grading systems are achieving popularity in academic institutions across the world, these programs evaluate written pros by simulation of human behavior and intelligence in order to relieve the burden of this tedious job called grading from educators leaving them free to educate. It evaluates properties of the essay such as linguistics, linear correlation, cohesion, grammar, sentence meaning and overall.

2.11.2 Statement of the problem

Automated essay grading consists of specialized computer programs that assign grades to essays using natural language processing. These systems can be as good, if not better than human graders in select circumstances. However, with the use of neural networks, it believed that automation can remove what little human error already occurs and make it efficient enough also

the use machine learning techniques over a sufficiently large training set to train system can make the systems better than the aforementioned system. Main goal is to improve the automated systems so that they can work perfectly like human graders.

2.11.3 Methodology

The model presented in the research starts from the Input representation layer which is used to generate a vector representation of the response of a student. The Memory addressing layer takes the student's response and divides into random samples and loads the pieces into the memory and assigns a weight to each memory piece. The memory reading layer then extracts the content from the memory depending upon the weights assigned by the previous layer. This produces the output state. The output layer then produces a prediction based upon the output state. The prediction now determines the grade of the student.

2.11.4 Significance of the study

However, with the use of neural networks, we believe that the use of automation can remove what little human error already occurs and make it efficient enough and grade better than educators on quantifiable errors such as sentence structure and spelling/grammar errors, the structure of the essay etc. However, neural networks secret of success is due to its ability to learn multiple layers of neurons and each layer can transform the representation into a higher level of abstraction.

2.11.5 Limitation of the study

It founded that computer cannot grade poetry like human and it sometimes grades students with a little higher marks than they deserve, i.e. AES to some extent overestimated the quality of the essays.

2.12 Using Automatic Scoring Models to Detect Changes in Student Writing in an Intelligent Tutoring System

Authors: Crossley et al (2013)

2.12.1 Introduction

A key measure of academic success is writing proficiency (Kellogg and Raulerson, 2007). However, attaining writing proficiency is often difficult and elusive (National Commission on Writing 2003). Strategies used in writing instruction include planning, drafting, editing, summarizing, and revising. Teaching these strategies has proven effective in improving student writing, particularly for adolescent writers (Graham and Perin, 2007). This literature compares automated scoring increases and linguistic changes for student writers in two groups. The primary goal is to examine automated scoring differences in both groups from pretest to posttest essays to investigate score gains and linguistic development.

2.12.2 Statement of the problem

Attaining writing proficiency is often difficult and elusive (National Commission on Writing 2003). Teaching students on writing is not an easy task and it also time consuming, the research try to get the best method to train students to write in a proficient way.

2.12.3 Methodology

The WPal system allows students view lessons on each strategy, play practice games, and write practice essays for each of the modules it then provides holistic scores and automated, formative feedback based upon natural language input.

This system uses hierarchical classification. Such hierarchical classification affords the opportunity to provide formative feedback at different conceptual levels; the first hierarchical categorization is a function of those who meet a threshold for number of words (250 words) and number of paragraphs (three paragraphs). In the following stages, the model assumes that essays that meet and do not meet the thresholds can be characterized by different linguistic features, such assumptions lead to a number of machine learning algorithms that are calculated separately for each group. For instance essays in the group that do not meet basic thresholds are divided into high and low groups using linguistic features fed into a Discriminant Function Analysis (DFA). The essays in the low group are then further divided into low essays (scored a 1) and high essays (scored a 2). All remaining essays in the low group are classified as higher quality and assigned a score of 3. Essays that do meet the first threshold are also classified into low and high groups using

linguistic features fed into a DFA. The low group is then further classified into low essays (scored a 2) and high essays (scored a 3). Essay in the high group are also divided into low essays (scored a 4) and high essays (scored a 5). That how the grading works

2.12.4 Significance of the study

The Automated writing evaluation (AWE) systems improve students writing skills by providing opportunities for students to practice writing and receive feedback in the classroom in the absence of a teacher. The systems improve motivation, users are skeptical about their scoring reliability (Grimes and Warschauer, 2010).

The literature also indicate that explicit strategy instruction and game practice mixed with essay writing and feedback lead to similar linguistic gains as essay writing and feedback alone.

2.12.5 Limitation of the study

Automated writing evaluation (AWE) systems generally depend on summative feedback at the expense of formative feedback (Roscoe et al., 2012).

2.13 Automated free text marking with Paperless School

Authors: Oliver and Grove-Stephenson (2002)

2.13.1 Introduction

The research is based on the approaches to address the challenge of providing both summative and formative assessments with little or no human intervention. Nevertheless provides an accurate view of the abilities of each student by averaging marks over a number of essays.

2.13.2 Statement of the problem

Highly valued activity for a teacher is to teach - yet in Britain, school teachers spend only 40% of their time in the classroom. Another 30% of their time is spent on marking. This activity does have value, but less so. British schools are traditionally wary of objective marking, so if there where to free up that 30%, then they must find an effective way, that teachers will trust, to mark essays and short text.

The proposed system is meant to facilitate the marking of large numbers of texts. This should enable considerable teacher resources to be freed up for other teaching tasks.

2.13.3 Methodology

Typical Things a teacher looks for in an answer are coverage of relevant concepts, evidence of understanding, evidence of evaluation, evidence of misconceptions. Bloom (1956) identified a six-element taxonomy of educational objectives, or competencies, which is widely used in the assessment of student work. The six are:

- i. **Knowledge:** remembering of previously learned material; recall (facts or whole theories);
- ii. **Comprehension:** grasping the meaning of material; interpreting (explaining or summarizing); predicting outcome and effects (estimating future trends).
- iii. **Application:** ability to use learned material in a new situation; apply rules, laws, methods, theories.
- iv. **Analysis:** breaking down into parts; understanding organization, clarifying, concluding.
- v. **Synthesis:** ability to put parts together to form a new whole; unique communication; set of abstract relations.
- vi. **Evaluation:** ability to judge value for purpose; base on criteria; support judgment with reason. (No guessing).

The proposed taxonomy system called bloom uses 3 out of the taxonomies

- i. Knowledge (K): The system identifies concepts in the student's essay, and evaluating their relevance to the subject area.
- ii. Understanding (U): Comprehension, Application, Analysis and Synthesis. Each of these then breaks down into a number of skills such as separating or identifying components and rearranging elements.
- iii. Evaluation (E): Here the system simply counts adjectives and adverbs.

The systems works like this, on submission, the student essay is sent to the server, together with information about the task, in order to identify the correct master texts for comparison. The student essay is then compared against each relevant master text to derive a number of parameters which reflect knowledge and understanding as exhibited by the student, the individual parameters computed during the analysis phase are then combined in a numerical expression to yield the

assignment's grade, the output from the marking process is then passed back to the client for presentation to the teacher. This includes details on sections of the essay which are particularly good (or bad) in relation to the K, U, and E factors.

2.13.4 Significance of the study

The Paperless School system is designed primarily for day-to-day, low stakes testing of essay and short-text student inputs nevertheless provides an accurate view of the abilities of each student by averaging marks over a number of essays.

2.13.5 Limitation of the study

Things that are identified as fall back of the system are

- i. There is no clear set of rules for selecting master texts.
- ii. Graduate and postgraduate-level material has so far proved difficult to auto grading with any accuracy.
- iii. Misspellings and bad grammar can throw the system out.

2.14 Get IT Scored using AutoSAS - An Automated System for Scoring Short Answers

Authors: Kumar et al (2019)

2.14.1 Introduction

Essays and other types of writing practices have been extensively used for evaluation purposes. The essays and short answers written by the students in the exams determine their future colleges and hence have a career wide impact. A school's reputation is often determined by the scores of its graduating students, which in turn is impacted by how well they have been taught to write their essays and short answers (Dale and Krueger 2002)

The introduction of the automated Short Answer Scoring (SAS) which is fast, scalable, and accurate provides economic advantages to testing companies and state-wide corporations. These systems reduce the economic and time burden of getting each response checked by human graders close to zero, bringing down the cost and effort.

2.14.2 Statement of the problem

It has been noted that about 30% of a teacher's time is spent in evaluating students that subsequently translates to close to 4.02 Billion Dollars per year coming from the taxpayers (Mason and Grove-Stephensen 2002). In addition, one often hears about biases in marking students based on region, religion, and ethnicity. Automated scoring systems can possibly aid in uprooting any such biases from the education system.

2.14.3 Methodology

The quality of text from the perspective of scoring short answers is dependent on many factors, some of them being content, grammar, vocabulary, flow, coherence of ideas and relevance to the topic. The system is primarily focused on utilizing natural language processing (NLP) which provides part of speech (POS) tagging, weighting keywords, prompt and lexical overlap.

2.14.4 Significance of the study

The system provides raw feedback, the students can assess their weak areas, using the feedback, and they can improve their writing before submitting the final document. The system can also be used as an alternative as well as to augment the feedback that teachers provide while they grade student responses.

2.14.5 Limitation of the study

The sentence length indicate the complexity of the sentence, with longer sentences requiring greater use of working memory and hence being more difficult to understand. The AutoSAS also lacks is comments review.

2.15 An Overview of Automated Scoring of Essays

Author: Dikli (2006)

2.15.1 Introduction

Automated Essay Scoring (AES) is defined as the computer technology that evaluates and scores the written prose (Shermis & Barrera, 2002). Teachers responding to student's paper can be of burden particularly when the students are large in number because they would have to grade the essay and give feedback to each student's essay; this is also waste lot of time.

2.15.2 Statement of the problem

The purpose of this research is to provide an overview of current approaches to automated essay scoring, finding more way to make the system provide accurate results. The paper lists the limitation and advantages of different automation systems.

2.15.3 Methodology

Different systems are used in accessing essay with different methods, below is a list of them:

- i. **Project Essay Grader (PEG):** PEG uses proxy measures to predict the intrinsic quality of the essays. Proxies refer to the particular writing construct such as average word length, essay length, number of semicolons or commas, and so on (Kukich, 2000 et al).
- ii. **Intellimetric and Myaccess:** IntelliMetric, an AES system developed by Vantage Learning, is known as the first essay scoring tool that was based on artificial intelligence (AI) (Shermis & Barrera, 2002). Like e-rater, IntelliMetric relies on NLP, which determines “the meaning of a text by parsing the text in known ways according to known rules conforming to the rules of English language”. MY Access is known as the instructional application of IntelliMetric, it is a web-based writing assessment tool.
- iii. **Intelligent Essay Assessor (IEA):** This automated system analyzes and scores an essay using a semantic text analysis method called Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA) (Lemaire & Dessus, 2001). Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA) is defined as “a statistical model of word usage that permits comparisons of the semantic similarity between pieces of textual information”.
- iv. **E-Raters and Criterion:** It analyzes the quality of an essay by identifying linguistic features in the text (Burstein & Marcu, 2000). E-rater uses natural language processing (NLP) techniques, which identify specific lexical and syntactic cues in a text, to analyze essays. The Natural language processing has four categories of language tasks which

include speech recognition, syntactic analysis, discourse analysis and information extraction, and machine translation. Criterion relies on Educational Testing Service (ETS) technologies called “e-rater” and “Critique” Writing Analysis tools.

2.15.4 Significance of the study

AES systems are developed to assist teachers in low-stakes classroom assessment as well as testing companies and states in large-scale high-stakes assessment. They are mainly used to help overcome time, cost, reliability, and generalizability issues in writing assessment (Bereiter, 2003 et al).

2.15.5 Limitation of the study

The automated grading systems have been criticized for lacking human interaction, vulnerability to cheating and their need for a large corpus of sample text to train the system (Chung & O’Neil, 1997).

2.16 Contrasting Automated and Human Scoring of Essays

Author: Zhang (2013)

2.16.1 Introduction

The interest in automated scoring of essays is not new and has recently received additional attention; essay scoring has traditionally relied on human raters, who understand both the content and the quality of writing. However, raise questions about the viability of relying on human scoring alone. This scoring method is expensive, requires extensive logistical efforts, and depends on less-than-perfect human judgment. Nonetheless, human labor cannot simply be replaced with machines, since human scoring and automated scoring have different strengths and limitations.

2.16.2 Statement of the problem

Human grading students’ method is expensive, requires extensive logistical efforts, and depends on less-than-perfect human judgment. The published research has few in-depth comparisons of the advantages and limitations of automated and human scoring. The sufficient

knowledge about the strengths and weaknesses of each scoring method is needed in order to prevent misuse in a testing program.

2.16.3 Methodology

Human grade using below methods to grade

- i. Cognitively process the information given in a text.
- ii. connect it with their prior knowledge
- iii. Based on their understanding of the content, make a judgment on the quality of the text.

The automation system uses natural Language processing.

2.16.4 Significance of the study

Some of the strengths of scoring by human graders is that they able to recognize and appreciate a writer's creativity and style (e.g., artistic, ironic, rhetorical), as well as evaluate the relevance of an essay's content to the prompt. A human rater can also judge an examinee's critical thinking skills, including the quality of the argumentation and the factual correctness of the claims made in the essay.

Automated scoring has the potential to provide solutions to some of the obvious shortcomings in human essay scoring (e.g., rater drift). These systems work exclusively with variables that can be extracted and combined mathematically. Humans, on the other hand, make holistic decisions under the influence of many interacting factors. Compare to human scoring lies in its efficiency, absolute consistency in applying the same evaluation criteria across essay submissions and over time, as well as its ability to provide fine-grained, instantaneous feedback. Computers are neither influenced by external factors (e.g., deadlines) nor emotionally attached to an essay. It would be quite difficult for human raters to offer analytical feedback immediately for large numbers of essays. The system can also detect inauthentic authorship.

2.16.5 Limitation of the study

The limitations, to begin with, qualified human raters must be recruited. Next, they must be instructed in how to use the scoring rubric and their rating competencies must be certified prior to engaging in operational grading. Finally, they must be closely monitored (and retrained if necessary) to ensure the quality and consistency of their ratings. (See Baldwin, Fowles, &

Livingston, 2005, for ETS's policies on performance assessment scoring.). Obviously, involving humans in grading such high volumes, especially in large-scale assessments, can be labor intensive, time consuming, and expensive.

2.17 Design and Implementation of an Automatic Scoring Subjective Question System Based on Domain Ontology

Author: NaWang (2013)

2.17.1 Introduction

With the rapid development of computer technology, the Computer Aided Test (CAT) that can compensate for the disadvantages of the traditional test system is gaining increasing concern. The automatic scoring technology which is used for objective questions has been applied in the large-scale examination systems because it is fashionable and mature. An automatic scoring system full of objective questions is no longer enough to evaluate the learning effect in that it cannot test the student's ability completely. For example, an examinee can select an answer randomly when he or she does not really understand the meaning of the questions. There is another reason to be pointed. Now, the assessment of subjective questions mainly depends on manual labor. The result is influenced by some factors, such as the calligraphy of the examinees, the working conditions of the teachers and so on. Besides, computers can be used in the evaluation of subject questions with the high speed and perfect performance.

2.17.2 Motivation

These automatic scoring algorithms are realized by evaluating the similarity of the student's answer and the standard one textually. However, the differences in the students' modes of expression and comprehension abilities lead to the answers of the subject problems are not unique. When a student describes the same thing by using different choices of words or pronouns.. Studies on automatic scoring algorithms have become prominent in academia at home and abroad.

2.17.3 Methodology

Any method of assessment must be judged on validity, fairness, and reliability. An instrument is valid if it actually measures the trait that it purports to measure. It is fair if it does not, in effect, penalize or privilege any one class of people. It is reliable if its outcome is repeatable, even when irrelevant external factors are altered. Before computers entered the picture, high-stakes essays were typically given scores by two trained human raters. If the scores differed by more than one point, a third, more experienced rater would settle the disagreement. In this system, there is an easy way to measure reliability by inter-rater agreement. If raters do not consistently agree within one point, their training may be at fault. If a rater consistently disagrees with whichever other raters look at the same essays, that rater probably needs more training.

2.17.4 Objective

Ontology plays a backbone for meaning-centered reconfiguration of syntactic structure, which is one aspect of semantic technology. It is necessary to establish an automatic scoring subjective question system. Ontology plays an important role in soft engineering. Shower of technical terms offered by ontology can be communicated by users.

2.17.5 Contribution to knowledge

An automatic scoring subjective question system based on domain ontology has been established according to the theoretical studies above. The domain dictionary loads automatically when the program starts.

2.17.6 Limitations

Based on the computation and the result of the experiments, an automatic assessment system is built. Of course, the parameter settings used in the evaluation should be changed for different subjects in the actual application. In the further research, the algorithm parameter correction may allow the system to malfunction when the parameters are not intact.

2.18 Semantic Driven Electronic Examination System for Subjective Questions

Author: Zubairu (2018)

2.18.1 Introduction

Examination is an important process for the evaluation of teaching and learning activities for the completion of teaching and learning where level of information from the instructor is evaluated to assess either the teaching or the learning process along all levels. Since the inception of education, there have been several techniques for examination process. The evolution and technology advancement have led to the emergence and popularity of electronic examination system. E-examination is the utilization of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) equipment and devices for an assessment or evaluation of knowledge. It is an assessment approach mediated by electronic technology and personal computer is a vital component of the system. It allows examiner(s) to author and plan examinations through the computer system where responses are electronically recorded and assessed. The aim is to make examination or assessment process faster and efficient.

2.18.2 Motivation

Despite making judgments on a common dimension, raters may be influenced by their attitudes, their cultural background, and their political and economic views. Since AES models are designed to learn by analyzing human-graded essays. It makes the System easier to use.

2.18.3 Methodology

In the existing e-examination platform, a user might input a term or phrase as the correct answer of choice and which is unknown, the system would check the WordNet database for a set of matches and determine if the designated answer is among the sun set of the user choice.

2.18.4 Objective

Assessing the learning of a student is interesting and important affair that requires diligence. Online assessment is gaining popularity and acceptance by many examination bodies and higher institutions of learning. However, most of the existing online assessment supports only objective type of questioning in form of multiple-choice questions. The scope of this type of question is

limited to perception and retention without demanding the student to be effective in his/her thinking capacity.

2.18.5 Contribution to knowledge

Therefore, education experts suggest on evaluating the students by adopting a hybrid approach That incorporates both the objective as well as subjective types of questioning methodologies.

2.18.6 Limitations

The electronic examination system for subjective question is limited to some sensitive errors which affects the syntax in matching and evaluation of the correct answer to the system. This capability is still lacking in the current subjective e-examination system which allows the current system to malfunction. However, answers evaluation for the same question is highly subjective and different instructors may have different views.

2.19 Subjective Questions Automatic Scoring Algorithm in Intelligent Tutoring System

Author: LiZhiping, (2013)

2.19.1 Introduction

With the development and popularization of computer and network technology, many courses examination have been able to on the computer. Network Exam has not only convenient organization but also can work anytime, anywhere and can quickly and objectively given test scores. It reduces the test cost. Thus, it will be the future trend of the development in large-scale examination. The ideal exam system not only include objective questions (multiple-choice question, determine the question, fill in the blank), but also include subjective questions (short answer, prove, computing, programming questions). The automatic scoring algorithms of objective questions use the student's answer and standard answer to compare. The results of this comparison are consistent, and then the answer is correct or wrong answers. It implements easy.

There is not an examination system which is good to complete its automatic scoring because of the answer characteristics and complexity in the subjective question. The automatic scoring subjective questions related theory and knowledge which are the theory of artificial intelligence, pattern recognition, natural language understanding etc. Lot of technical question need to be solved and thus it become a technical difficulty in the network examination system.

2.19.2 Motivation

Subjective questions in the answer are generally described by the language, but everyone has different levels of understanding of the knowledge and the expression is also inconsistent. Even if the student's answer is accurate, it is difficult to fully consistent with the standard answer.

Accurate ratings of subjective questions are almost impossible just as objective questions.

Analyze scoring teachers in the review the subjective questions, design algorithms and simulate scoring teachers this thinking activity. Then to analyze the students' answer and the standard answer, it can give the student's actual score.

2.19.3 Methodology

In this study, to resolve the close degree of students' answers and the standard answer that the problem can be seen as the student answer and standard answer string. The following will to define the concept of one-way nearness. Decomposed into a string to a single character, and they form an ordered collection is called a fuzzy set, $U = \{u_1, u_2, u_3 \dots u_n\}$ is called the domain. On the domain U of all fuzzy subset consisting denoted as $F(U)$ (Also called fuzzy power set). To measure the closeness of two fuzzy set introduce the concept of a one-way approach degree.

Definition 1: Let $U = \{U_1, U_2, U_3 \dots, U_n\}, A, B \in F(U)$

If the mapping $\delta: F(U) \times F(U) \rightarrow [0, 1]$, satisfiesthecondition:

$$\delta(A, A) = 1$$

$\delta(B, B) = 1$ \square If the $A B C$ or $A B C$, then $\delta(A, B) \geq \delta(A, C)$ and said $\delta(A, B)$, A is close to the B unidirectional closeness degree.

Definition 2: Let A, B is the string, A contain n characters, $\delta(A, B)$ represent A close to the B unidirectional closeness. In accordance with the order from left to right, the effective sum number of set A in each element in the Set B refers to m , $\delta(A, B) = m/n$. It is easy to verify that it meets

the definition of a one-way approach degree. The introduction of a one-way approach degree in the scoring of subjective questions, the standard answer string denoted by A_0 , students answer string is denoted by A , A_0 and A are two fuzzy sets. So, the standard answers the A_0 and Students answer A , one-way approach degree $\delta(A_0, A)$.

2.19.4 Objective

The automatic scoring rating is the basic function and inevitable choice of the network test system. Automatic scoring of subjective questions is a key technology in the network test system.

2.19.5 Contribution to knowledge

Analyze scoring teachers in the review the subjective questions, design algorithms and simulate scoring teachers this thinking activity and to resolve the close degree of students' answers and the standard answer that the problem can be seen as the student answer and standard answer string.

2.19.6 Limitations

In this research, one of the disadvantages is a one-way approach degree in detail and automatic scoring algorithm of subjective question and the design algorithm. Preliminary it affects the goal of the system and allows the system to work slowly for accurate ratings of subjective questions and to solve many technical problems in the future.

2.20 Automatic Essay Scoring System

Author: Zhang (2017)

2.20.1 Introduction

Essay is considered to play an essential role in education. One of important problems in essay grading is subjectivity (Valenti et al., 2003) that is hard to be perfectly avoid. Subjective can be reduced by taking multiple graders' opinions into consideration but it is highly cost and inefficient. An automatic scoring (AES) system would be fair and consistent in grading efficiently. There are mainly two types of AES system: feature selection-based machine learning approaches and neural network approaches which capture complex patterns from context. Neural network performs better

than traditional machine learning on tasks like pattern recognition, natural language understanding so that it becomes more and more popular in designing artificial intelligent systems.

2.20.2 Motivation

The task of automated essay scoring (AES) is usually treated as a supervised learning problem. The score of essays can be treated as continuous values, especially for a large range of possible scores. AES models are trained to minimize the difference between generated scores and reference scores graded by human.

2.20.3 Methodology

The study of Automatic scoring system models uses the following method below to achieve its system:

- i. Neural Network Approach: With the advent of distributed and GPU systems, neural network-based approaches have become popular for AES system. Neural network-based approaches offer an ability to capture complex patterns, semantic and syntactic features without manually feature engineering.

2.20.4 Objectives

According to comparison between several structures and mechanisms, the most proper way to represent documents is to treat it hierarchically. Attention mechanism performs well on weighting key words and key sentences. Larger datasets with possible special cases are required to train a reliable AES system.

2.20.5 Contribution to knowledge

Neural Network Approach and Machine learning approach, with the advent of distributed and GPU systems, neural network-based approaches have become popular and have contributed to the AES system development.

2.20.6 Limitations

AES models does not grade the scores manually, selection-based machine learning approaches and neural network approaches which capture complex patterns from context.

Table 1: *Descriptions of Some Common Human-Rater Errors and Biases*

Severity/ Leniency	Refers to a phenomenon in which raters make judgments on a common dimension, but some raters tend to consistently give high scores (leniency) while other raters tend to consistently give low scores (severity), thereby introducing systematic biases.
Scale Shrinkage	Occurs when human raters don't use the extreme categories on a scale.
Inconsistency	Occurs when raters are either judging erratically, or along different dimensions, because of their different understandings and interpretations of the rubric.
Halo Effect	Occurs when the rater's impression from one characteristic of an essay is generalized to the essay as a whole.
Stereotyping	Refers to the predetermined impression that human raters may have formed about a particular group that can influence their judgment of individuals in that group.
Perception Difference	Appears when immediately prior grading experiences influence a human rater's current grading judgments.
Rater Drift	Refers to the tendency for individual or groups of raters to apply

inconsistent scoring criteria over time.

CHAPTER 3

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION TO THE CHAPTER

In this chapter, I talked about the system analysis and design related to the development of an unsupervised automated subjective and objective scoring system, I discuss the statistical model behind the objective of the scoring system in my research.

3.2 JUSTIFICATION OF THE NEW SYSTEM

Based on the above issues provided by this traditional way of grading students there is a need to create an automated assessment tool for automated systems that would at least be consistent in the way it scores essay and fast in grading. With this, the time-saving and enormous cost could be achieved. The proposed system is meant to solve all the problems associated with the traditional way of grading students; the system is an online website which consists of below modules:

- i. **Admin module:** This module is meant for admins. In this module, the admin would be allowed to post both objective and subjective questions and answers based on a certain course, to remove the question or edit it, they would also have the ability to add faculties, grades, courses, and departments. He or she would also have the ability to see the grades of each student that took the exam. The admin module is divided into two parts, the part that has to do with the objective question; this is where questions that have options are handled using PHP and MySQL. The second part is the part that as to

do with subjective questions, this part is handled by python and its libraries like NLTK. The admin would also have to approve students that register on the website before the student would have access to the student's dashboard.

- ii. **User module:** This module is meant for students; this is where he or she takes the exam and write his or her answers in the provided boxes or choose from the provided options, also in this module student would have the ability to register which course he or she wants to take for that year, it only courses he or she register that he or she would only have access to the questions and only courses related to his or her department that he or she would be able to register. All these activities are carried out from the student dashboard, once the student visit the website URL then click on log in, he or she would be prompted to input his or her login details, if the details are correct then the student is taken into the dashboard where he or she can perform any of the activities explained above. If a user does not have a login detail he or she would have to register and then wait for his or her approval from an admin before he or she can log in. Below is the use case diagram showing all the processes both modules can perform.

Figure 3.1: The use case diagram

3.3 System Model:

The top-down model was adopted in designing the automated objective and subjective scoring system. The results of the analysis were broken down into different component where the design is stated from the main component into the elementary component. The system is categorized into three (3) major sub systems which are, lecturer subsystem, student subjective, and compiler check.

Figure 3.2: System Design Approach

3.4 Methodology

The proposed system would solve all the problems the current system has, all that the admin needs to do is to set the questions online. The system is a web application in which we would design the front-end with HTML, CSS, Bootstrap, and JavaScript, the backend with PHP and MySQL and we would use PhpMyAdmin as the database. I will start by creating the basic template that all the website other parts would follow using HTML ,CSS for the attractiveness and bootstrap for the responsiveness, then I will design the dashboard for the all the users of the system such as the admin, students, using HTML ,CSS for the attractiveness and bootstrap for the responsiveness as well as JavaScript to make it interactive, then I will design the form where by students trying to apply for the exam can input all their details and submit it, all the inputs would be validated and the details of the student would be visible on the admin dashboard, also once an student apply and get approved by the admin, he or she would have access to the dashboard where he can perform all task a student is allowed to perform.

Also I will design the log in page form which users of the system i.e the admin and student would input their password and username to access their dashboard, once they input their details to login the system would validate the input using php functions such as the mysql to avoid any attack attempt such as SQL injection, XSS attack etc., once the inputted text are validated the code would automatically create a session for the user and then the system checks for the user's role in the system so as to take the person to the dashboard pertaining to the login details else the user is

prevented from logging in. All inputs sent from the input box would be validated and sent into the database using a prepared statement in combination with my MySQL which helps prevent injections.

Below is the website structure:

Figure 3.3: The website structural design

Starting from the student dashboard, the students would be given below functionalities:

- i. **Edit profile:** Here the user inputs are validated and each input is corresponding to the questions asked, i.e., in a form box where the student is asked to input age, the form box should only allow numbers to be inputted. Any time the user attempt to input text then the system should show an error message, once the user has inputted all the details and the details inputted are validated then the inputs would be sent into the database and stored in the student table using a prepared statement in combination with my MySQL which helps prevent injections.
- ii. **Register course:** Here the students would be given the ability to register courses for a particular year, and the courses would be selected from a drop-down list, this list is from the database that store only courses the admin adds to the system. The course that is not added to the system by the admin would not show on the student's dashboard. Students would also be able to remove courses they register in case they made a mistake. And a limit would be set on the total course unit to be registered per year. Once the user has selected all the course he or she wants to register for that year and the inputted values are validated then the inputs would be sent into the database and stored in the student course table with

- the student id and course id (as reference) using prepared statement in combination with my MySQL which helps prevent injections.
- iii. **View result:** Here the student would be able to view their result based on the course they register and the year they registered it, this result would be gotten from the result table and queried with the student id, course id and year. Students would not be able to edit the results.
 - iv. **Take exam and test:** The student would be provided with access to the questions the admin added for exam or test, once the student takes the exam he or she is not given another chance to take it again and there is going to be time limit and days to take the exam, the limit is set by the admin. Once the exam or test is taken by the student the student result is stored in the result table with his or her student id, the year and course id as the foreign key.
 - v. Now the admin's dashboard functionalities are explained below:
 - vi. **Edit profile:** Here the user inputs are validated and each input is corresponding to the questions asked, i.e., in a form box where the lecturer is asked to input age, the form box should only allow numbers to be inputted. Any time the user attempt to input text then the system should show an error message, once the user has inputted all the details and the details inputted are validated then the inputs would be sent into the database and stored in the admin table using a prepared statement in combination with my MySQL which helps prevent injections.
 - vii. **Register course:** Here the admin would be given the ability to add courses to the system. Admin would also be able to remove courses they registered in case they made a mistake. Once the admin has inputted all the details of the courses and the inputted values are validated then the inputs would be sent into the database and stored in the course table using a prepared statement in combination with my MySQL which helps prevent injections.
 - viii. **View result:** The admin would be able to view the result of all the students that took a course.
 - ix. **Create questions:** Here the ability to write, edit and view questions with its answer and upload it for certain courses exam and these questions would be validated and saved in the questions table in the database with the course id as the foreign key.

- x. **Add admin:** The admin would be able to add other admins, view and delete them and also edit their details. These details would be stored in the admin table in the database.

Below is a list of technologies needed to build the proposed system:

- i. HTML (Hypertext mark-up language): This is needed to create the text part of the website, bring images into the website and make pages linked together.
- ii. CSS (Cascading style sheet): This is needed to make the website look attractive through the use of color and other functionalities it has.
- iii. JavaScript: This is used to make the page interactive.
- iv. Python: This is used in creating the natural language processing system.
- v. PHP: This is used to connect the database to the website.
- vi. Bootstrap: This is used to make the website responsive.
- vii. Wampserver: This is where the website is tested offline before taken online.

From all that is mentioned above we can see that the proposed system is feasible, it economically feasible based on that the things needed to build the system can be easily gotten and they are not expensive. It is operationally feasible since all students are used to the use of the website on their laptop and smartphones, and also it technically feasible since all the technologies needed is available.

In order to satisfy the above-mentioned requirements, our system tests student programs by the following way.

- i. **Compiler Check:** If there are syntactical or grammatical errors in the source code, it is not possible to test the program accurately. Therefore, our system tries to compile a student program first of all. If the compilation fails by any reasons, the error messages of the compiler are displayed to the student after stopping scoring process.
- ii. **JUnit Test:** If the assignment demands to write a class or a method except for a main, JUnit test is used. JUnit is a framework to write repeatable test methods, each of which contains assertions for testing expected results. It is ordinary used to test public classes and methods, but it also can be used for private classes and methods with the reflection API. Our system executes test methods provided by the instructor.

- iii. **Result Test:** Every program written for assignments is expected to input data from the keyboard and to display the result on the screen. It is usually done by a main method written by a student or given by the instructor. We can conduct a test by comparing the results of a student program and the reference program provided by the instructor. Our system uses the redirection to supply the input data and to obtain the result, and then compares the results by means the regular expression API.

Figure: 3.4 Process Flow for Scoring

Figure 3.5: Overall System Architecture

3.5 Data Collection

3.5.1 Database design and the model with relationship

The database we are going to use for the proposed system is MySQL database, the database is meant to hold all the data from the website, data like text, files, integers, etc. Based on what the proposed system is to do, below data type would be used in the database:

- i. Integer: To store integer values, this holds data like matric number, ids, admin number, phone numbers, etc.
- ii. Varchar: To store strings, letters, characters, this holds the names, email, gender, faculty name, department name, etc.
- iii. Timestamp: this is used to store time, this hold dates and time.

Based on the information we would collect from the website, we have divided the information into tables with different names such as faculty, department, students, etc, this tables are connected together based on the relationship between them, the diagram below explains in full details the relationship and cardinalities between each table.

The automated Objective and Subjective scoring system uses My SQL, for its database. The database contains tables that hold its important data and their specifications. Some of the tables are shown below:

3.5.2 Database Structure

We created eleven 1 database but 12 tables for this Postgraduate management system:

Table 3.1 Administrator table

Field	Type	Null	Key	Default	Extra
Id	int(11)	NO	PRI	NULL	auto_increment
user_username	varchar(20)	NO	MUL	NULL	
User_password	varchar(50)	NO		NULL	
fullnamae	varchar(50)	NO		NULL	
Staff_id	Varchar(20)	NO		NULL	
dept_id	Varchar(10)	NO		NULL	
Role	Varchar(50)	NO		NULL	
Phone_no	Varchar(50)	NO			

Table3.1 represents the table structure of admin table. Here all admin personal records are stored and access.

Table 3.2 Course table

Field	Type	Null	Key	Default	Extra
Id	int(11)	NO	PRI	NULL	auto_increment
optCode	varchar(10)	NO		NULL	
course_title	varchar(150)	NO		NULL	

Table 3.2 represents the table structure of course database. All courses that students are to offer are stored and accessed here. The courses sub-system uses this database to manage courses.

Table 3.3 Student profile table

Field	Type	Null	Key	Default	Extra
matricNumber	varchar(25)	NO	UNI	NULL	
fullName	varchar(150)	NO		NULL	
gender	Varchar(10)				
level_id	int(11)	YES	MUL	NULL	
department_id	int(11)	YES	MUL	NULL	
created_at	Timestamp	NO		CURRENT_TIMESTAMP	
updated_at	Timestamp	NO		0000-00-00 00:00:00	

Table 3.3 represents the field structure of student table. The student database is where the information needed from all students is been stored and accessed by the administrator for updates.

Table 3.4 Semester table

Field	Type	Null	Key	Default	Extra
SemesterID	int(11)	NO	PRI	NULL	auto_increment
cSemester	varchar(25)	NO		NULL	

Table 3.4 represents the table structure of Semester database. The semester database is where the information needed from a particular Semester is stored.

Table 3.5 Classes table

Field	Type	Null	Key	Default	Extra
cClass	Varchar(20)	NO	PRI	NULL	auto_increment

Table 3.5 represents the table structure of Dept. table. The Dept. database is where the information needed from a particular Dept. is stored.

Table 3.6 Course_listing table

Field	Type	Null	Key	Default	Extra
cCode	varchar(20)	NO	PRI	NULL	auto_increment
cTitle	varchar(200)	NO	UNI	NULL	

Table 3.6 represents the table structure of course title and course code table. This shows the table where course details can be found.

Table 3.7 Course_option table

Field	Type	Null	Key	Default	Extra
Id	int(11)	NO	PRI	NULL	auto_increment
optCode	varchar(10)	NO		NULL	
cOption	varchar(150)	NO		NULL	

Table 3.7 represents the table structure of section database. Here all Section records are stored and access.

Table 3.8 Question_tmp table

Field	Type	Null	Key	Default	Extra
Id	int(11)	NO	PRI	NULL	auto_increment
Qid	bigint (20)	NO		NULL	
Options_selected	Varchar(250)	NO		NULL	
MatricnNumber	Varchar(30)	NO		NULL	
cCode	Varchar (20)	NO		NULL	
answer	Float			NULL	

cClass	Varchar(20)	NO		NULL	
cSession	Varchar(20)	NO		NULL	
cSemester	Varchar(10)	NO		NULL	
C_date_time	Varchar(30)	NO		NULL	

Table 3.8 represents the table structure of user login database

Table 3.8 questions_bank table

Field	Type	Null	Key	Default	Extra
Id	Bigint(20)	NO	PRI	NULL	Auto_increment
question	Longtext	NO		NULL	
optCode	Varchar(20)	NO		NULL	
cCode	Varchar(10)	NO		NULL	
cClass	Varchar(20)	NO		NULL	
cSemester	Varchar(20)	NO		NULL	
cSession	Varchar(20)	NO		NULL	
german	Tinyint(4)	NO		NULL	
Staff_id	Varchar(50)	NO		ADMIN	

Table 3.9 represent the questions storage table. This structure shows the way the structure table works

Table 3.10 question_settings

Field	Type	Null	Key	Default	Extra
Id	Int(11)	NO	PRI	NONE	Auto_increment
cCode	Varchar(20)	NO		NONE	
Max_questions	Int(11)	NO		0	
Exam_date	date	NO		NONE	
Exam_duration	time	NO		NONE	
Display_score	Tinyint(4)	NO		0	
Q_per_page	Tinyint(4)	NO		1	
C_instructions	text	NO		NONE	
cSession	varchar	NO		NONE	
eligibility	Tinyint(4)	NO		0	

Table 3.10 represent the question settings. The structure explain basics information and settings about the structure.

Table 3.11 question_options

Field	Type	Null	Key	Default	Extra
Id	Int(11)	NO	Pri	NONE	Auto_increment
Qid	Bigint(20)	NO		0	
Option	Text	NO		NONE	
Answer	Float	NO		0	

Table 3.11 represent the options part of the questions in the objectives part of the system.

Table 3.12 app_settings

Field	Type	Null	Key	Default	Extra
Id	Int(11)	NO	PRI	NONE	Auto_increment
organisation	varchar(20)	NO		0	
address	Varchar(200)	NO		NONE	
Phone_number	Varchar(50)	NO		0	
Email_address	Varchar(100)	NO			
Logo	Varchar(50)	NO			
Login_style	Tinyint(4)	NO			

Table 3.12 represent the login platform.

3.6 Architectural design

The design of the system has to do with the use of machine learning as well as PHP, based on the explanations given above the process the system would use in the scoring process as well as the full system design is summarized in the diagrams below:

Figure 3.1: The full system architecture

Figure 3.2: The Subjective Scoring model

Figure 3.2: Objective Scoring model

3.7 PROGRAM FLOWCHART

A flowchart is diagrammatic representation of a process. Instructions given to computers are usually broken down into sequence of step and executed one at a time. Flowcharts are very important aid in computer programming logic. It mostly helps the programmer learn how to design

program logic by using pictorial representations.

Program Flowchart of the Admin System

Program Flowchart of the Lecturer System

Program Flowchart of the Student System

3.7 Algorithm Design

i. **Subjective scoring model algorithm**

Step 1: The admin set a particular question and input the answer.

Step 2: Collect the student's answer

Step 3: Sentence preprocessing of both the student and lecturer answer

Step 3.1: Converting all letters to lower.

Step 3.2: Converting numbers into words

Step 3.3: Removing punctuations, accent marks, and other diacritics

Step 3.4: Removing white spaces

Step 3.5: Expanding abbreviations

Step 3.6: Removing stop words, sparse terms.

Step 4: Sentence segmentation of both the student and lecturer answer using spacy and NLTK library in python.

Step 5: Use of word2vec to get the vectors of the two sentences.

Step 6: Find the average of the vector in the two sentences.

Step7: Using cosine similarities to find the similarities from the average of the two sentence vector.

Step 8: Assign score based on the similarity gotten from step 7.

ii. **Objective scoring model algorithm**

Step 1: The admin set a particular question and input the answer.

Step 2: Collect the student's answer

Step 3: The system compare the option taken from the student's answer and the answer the admin set

Step 4: The student then assign 1 to every match that is the same in step 2.

Step 5: The system sum up the 1's from step 4.

Step 6: Assign score based the sun gotten from step 5.

Step7: Both the subjective and objective score are stored in the database and added together to get the student total score.

CHAPTER FOUR

SYSTEM DOCUMENTATION, IMPLEMENTATION AND TESTING

4.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter introduces the full documentation of the designed system. The underlying functionalities, representation of knowledge and production rules have adequately been elucidated in the preceding chapter. This chapter then describes the Installation procedure, Software launching (walk through), Software Testing, Hardware and Software requirements of any system that would implement it.

4.2 USER DOCUMENTATION

Network security is a foremost issue these days as the network usage is growing in multi-dimensions due to increased use of handheld devices. Intrusion Detection Systems can help detect malign intentions of network users, therefore our work compared bat with particle swarm algorithm to be assured of the one that has high Detection rate and false alarm rate without compromising the security of the host and the network.

4.2.1 SOFTWARE INSTALLATION

The setup of the software will be on a CD, it automatically runs as the CD is inserted into the system. The software installation wizard guides the user throughout the installation process. The software can be started through the program menu on the start menu.

4.2 THE USER INTERFACE

The user interface (UI) is the point of human-computer interaction and communication in a device. It is the way through which a user interacts with an application or website. The user interface for this program consists of 5 pages.

4.2.1 The Home Page

4.2.2 The Sign Up Page

This page enables students to register their selves by filling in the required details before they would be able to partake in the examination.

4.2.2 The Login Page

Already registered students or returning students will be able to access their dashboard by signing in with their registered matric number and password.

4.2.3 User Dashboard

The user dashboard is where a successful login direct user to, it displays the student profile and list available courses, it also has the logout button which enables a student to end his/her session on the website.

4.2.4 About Us Page

The about us page is also visible to users/student, it displays the history, vision and mission of the school

4.2.5 Contact Page

This page displays the available contact details to reach the school for support, it also has a simple contact form to enable users/students reach the support person faster.

4.3 The Admin Pages

This page/pages is only visible to staff/admin/ anyone who manages this program/website, it gives authority over the student pages, it enables staffs to manage courses, manipulate data, delete, report a student for malpractice or place a student on hold.

4.3.1 CPanel Login

4.3.2 Admin Interface

4.3.3 Student Registration Page

4.3.4 New Level

4.3.5 Department

4.3.6 Courses

4.3.7 Semester

4.4 CBT Section

4.4.1 Question

4.4.2 Course Settings

4.4.3 Course Registration

4.4.5 Test/Exam Activation

4.4.6 Malpractice

4.5 Report Session

4.5.1 Test/Exam Score

4.5.2 Class List

4.5.3 Attendance

4.5.4 List of Malpractices

4.5.5 Import

4.5.5.1 Import Student Record

4.5.5.2 Import Test/Exam

4.5.5.3 Import Questions

4.5.6 Export Records

4.5.6.1 Export Students Record

4.5.6.2 Export Student Test/Exam

4.5.6.3 Export Questions

4.6 Tools Section

4.6.1 Delete Question

4.6.2 Delete Records

CHAPTER 5

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

SUMMARY

Computer Based Test/Exam is the way of improving examination activities fast and efficient. This software is interactive and user friendly has all the command controls that would allow student successfully accomplish the exams have been implemented using the simplest graphic styles. All users' needs to do are to register by fill up the signup form with their Id, Name, Phone, Email and Password. The students and controller both have to pass authentication to log into the system. The most beautiful feature is to monitor the exam from control room and instantly got the total examination picture

CONCLUSION

Using an open-source language gives us more flexibility, but at the same time it required more time to be programmed. The proposed Computer Based Test can be easily adopted by universities and institutions in order to make the exam more secure and more flexible. The system is subdivided into two main subsystems (student and administrator) that are designed to give the system maximum benefit by demonstrating carefully each subsystem service. The administrator's functions are clearly identified to be able to manipulate user's information such as add (register), delete users and managing the exam materials and content such as add, delete questions, Thus the proposed system is easy and flexible because for future maintenance and development because each subsystem can be handled separately without influence on other system.

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